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GRADES I LEARNERS IN PASACAO DISTRICT, DIVISION OF
CAMARINES SUR: BASIS FOR MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT**

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Instruction Materials for English Intervention in the Grades I Learners in Pasacao District, Division of Camarines Sur: Basis for Material Development

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to develop instructional materials and field test these materials to measure the effect of literacy intervention on the performance of Grade 1 learners of Pasacao District, Division of Camarines Sur during the school 2018-2019. Experimental Design specifically the Pre-test and Post-test Nonrandom Design research was used by the researcher to address the different problems pose in this study. Statistical analysis of the data which requires the use of the mean and t-test yielded the following results and findings. Demographic of respondents in terms of gender, the literacy level of early grade learners in pre-test and post-test ranges from average to very high. There is a highly significant difference exist between the pre-test and post-test scores of learners. According to the findings of the study the female was 12 out of 23 learners or 52.17 percent and the male was 11 out of 23 or 47.78 percent. On the other hand the obtained mean in pretest is 14.1304 while 24.8261 in posttest. The mean of scores showed that the increase of literacy level is from average to very high. The Computed t of 35.918 and its probability value of .000 at .05 level of significance is interpreted that there is a highly significant difference exist between the pre-test and post-test scores of learners. Null hypothesis claiming that there is no significant difference on the literacy levels in pre-test and post-test is therefore rejected.

Keywords: *intervention, material, development, english*

Introduction

There are teachers' activities outside the school which decrease the quality time for learners to learn the language. Various activities and quasi teaching concerns like attendance to seminars, workshops and trainings lessen teachers' time in the classroom. Lessons are not delivered as planned because of interruptions beyond the control of the teacher.

The English proficiency of Filipino learners is continually declining over the years as shown in the low performance in national assessment in their competency in the use of the English language. Learners have great difficulty in expressing their ideas in the classroom and in writing which could also be attributed to the utter neglect of developing the writing competencies of the students. Classroom activities are neglected or are not enough to help the students develop their writing competence.

Learners have writing problems in expressing themselves systematically and logically. This lack of skills as one of the most common complaints students have when they encounter a particularly difficult assignment may be an outcome of neglecting one's studies for a considerable period of time, poor education or something else.

The questions on writing difficulty of learners have become the focus of some researchers. However, the problem remains unsolved. There are three reasons why so many children and youth find writing difficult like composing text is a complex and difficult undertaking that requires the deployment and coordination of multiple affective, cognitive, linguistic, and physical operations to accomplish goals associated with genre-specific conventions, audience needs, and author's communicative purposes.

It is along this light that the researcher will be motivated to develop learning materials to be able to address these problems encountered by some Grade 1 learners of Pasacao District, Division of Camarines Sur.

Research Questions

Generally, the purpose of this study is to develop instructional materials and to test these materials to measure the effect of literacy intervention on the performance of Grade 1 learners of Pasacao District, Division of Camarines Sur during the School Year 2018-2019. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents with regards to gender?
2. What is the literacy level of early grade learners in pretest and post-test?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of the performance of the grade one learners who were exposed to the materials in the pretest and in the post test?

Methodology

Research Design

This study focuses on the development of the materials specifically on literacy intervention learning material and field testing. In the field testing of the materials, Experimental Design, specifically the Pretest and Posttest single group design will be used.

Respondents

The study will be conducted in Pasacao District, Division of Camarines Sur. The study subjects will be the Grade 1 learners of Pasacao District, Division of Camarines Sur, School Year 2018-2019.

Instrument

In the conduct of this study, the researcher will use two (2) research instruments to measure the performance of the learners: 1) the developed instructional materials that will serve as the learning intervention to the learners and 2) the literacy test which measure the performance of the learners will be constructed by the researcher. This literacy test will be subjected to content-related validity and reliability tests.

Literacy Intervention Learning Material

The researcher-made literacy intervention learning material is a type of module which consists of activities design to improve the learners' literacy performance. Activities which include in this learning material focuses on the topics such as verbs.

On Materials Development

In designing, development and validation of this instructional learning materials, the researcher adapts the Johnsons System of Material Design Model. The model consists of three phases: the design phase, the development phase and the evaluation phase.

Design Phase

Conducts Survey on the Availability of Referenced Books and other Reading Materials

During the design phase, the researcher first will conduct a survey on the availability of referenced books and other reading materials. The purpose of this is to ensure that there are available references that contain activities and exercises suited for the literacy skills development of grade 1 learners. Furthermore, the conduct of survey on the availability of the references guides the researcher how to develop the learning material in terms of style and format.

During this phase, the researcher also will consider internet browsing and finding other supplementary materials which will be used as a guide and reference in the development of the proposed researcher made literacy learning intervention material. Through this, it guides the researcher as to the manner of presentation of the content of the module. The different types of literacy activities and exercises and its degree of difficulty will also be considered to bring content exercises suited for Grade 1 learners.

Selection of Materials

After a thorough examination of the different references and as well as internet websites, the researcher will choose the format, content and exercises will be included in the final draft of the proposed learning material.

The use of visual illustrations will be included in the learning material to give additional value and comprehension of the subject matter. Various types of activities and exercises were chosen. However, some of this materials and reference was adapted and modified by the researcher.

Preparing the Final Format for the Proposed Instructional Module

In preparing the final format for the proposed instructional module, grouping and listing of topics will serve as the basis in making the first draft of the module, taking into consideration the scope or coverage for each numeracy learning material. The proposed module covers the following topics on verbs.

Development Phase

Determining the Format

Considering the various learning materials, supplementary references from the Department of Education (DepEd) and some internet sources, this helps the researcher in determining the format in developing instructional materials. For presentation style, each instruction will be presented through the set of exercises which will hope to improve learners' literacy performance levels.

Development of Activities/Exercises

The development of activities/ exercises will be based from the different instructions that will be provided by the researcher in the learning material. Some of the exercises will be browsed by the researcher from the internet websites will be modified and adapted from the different authorities and experts in English. Consideration will be done, in the development of exercises as to its applicability in real-life situations.

Drawing/illustrating of Stimulating Materials

The researcher selects relevant illustrations to be incorporated in the learning material. Each exercise will supplement with illustrations

to motivate Grade 1 pupil's minds and develop their strengths and weaknesses in literacy areas.

As a whole, the materials that will be considered in the preparation of the instructional material are based on the needs and interests in academics of the Grade 1 learners especially on the topics to be identified by the researcher as difficult to the grade 1 learners. This facilitates good learning and interest of the Grade 1 learners.

After classifying the topics, instructional materials will be shown to peers and experts for content validation.

Validity/Evaluation Phase

The proposed instructional material will be subjected through the process of evaluation/ validation by identified evaluators. Peers, supervisors, administrators and members of Curriculum and Instructional Development of the Division of Camarines Sur are chosen to validate the developed materials.

On Field Testing

This portion deals with the presentation and discussions of the research design, the subjects of the study, the research instrument, the data gathering procedures, the conduct of the experiment, and the techniques for data analysis to be employed in this study.

Literacy Test Performance

This assessment tool consists of 30-item multiple choice test that is developed by the researcher. The items are divided in the different sub-topics such as verbs.

In constructing this test, the researcher carefully considers and follows the steps and principles in test construction, such as the planning stage, the dry run stage and the evaluation stage. The first step in planning the test is to determine the statement of the objectives. The objectives are formulated in relation to the topics included in the performance test.

After formulating the objectives, the researcher develops the table of specification. This table of specification serves as a guide while the researcher is constructing the test. The table of specification contains information as to the intended coverage of the test, the number of items the test as a whole and its component parts, and the weight of each component part, among others.

After table of specification is developed, the researcher will proceed to the development of test items. Various learning materials will be used as references in test construction. In this study, the researcher formulates sixty (60) items test twice as many as the final draft. These items are constructed following the guidelines in making multiple choice test items.

To establish the content related validity of the test, the researcher requests experts in literacy area to evaluate the test items. Then the items are edited to check grammatical errors in the statement of the stem and the alternatives. In order to achieve this, the researcher asks the assistance of the expert regarding this matter. After validation of the test, it will be reproduced and be given to the dry run respondents.

The Dry-Run Phase

After validity of the test will be established, the researcher conducts the dry run of the test.

In the dry run phase, 23 Grade 1 learners of Pasacao District, Division of Camarines Sur will be requested to take the test. They will be supplied with research questionnaire and they will be instructed to encircle the letter that corresponds to the correct answer.

They will be informed that they are not under time pressure to avoid any anxiety while taking the test. The dry run results will be subjected to item analysis and reliability tests.

Procedure

Item Analysis

After scoring the test, each item will be evaluated by estimating the item difficulty, assessing the discriminating power of each item and the effectiveness of each alternative. Item difficulty and item discrimination are often used as a criterion for the selection and refinement of test items.

The item analysis of the test will follow the Upper Lower Index Method.

The steps are:

1. Score the paper and rank it from the highest to the lowest according to the total score.
2. Separate the top 27% and the bottom 27% of the papers.
3. Tally the response made to each test item by each individual in the upper 27% group.
4. Tally the response made to each made to each test item by each individual in the lower 27% group.

5. Compute the percentage of the upper group that got the item right and call it U.
6. Compute the percentage of the lower group that got the item right and call it L.
7. Average the U and L percentage and the result is the difficulty index of the item.
8. Subtract the L percentage from the U percentage and the result is the discrimination index.

The discriminating power of the item in an achievement test refers to the degree to which it discriminates between learners with high and low achievements.

In this study, marginal items with moderate difficulty will be retained, but improved. Items needed revision and improvement will be retained, while those, which were not good items, will be rejected.

Reliability

Reliability as defined by Sevilla (1990) is the degree of consistency and precision a measuring instrument demonstrates. In this study, the reliability of the test will be used to determine using Kuder-Richardson Formula 21. The formula can easily be applied if the mean and the standard deviation obtained by the group will be determined.

The test had a reliability coefficient of 848 verbally described as high degree.

Administering Pre-Test

A pre-test containing the items on literacy performance test will be administered to the subjects of the study. This is to determine the level of literacy skills of the participants before treatment.

During Treatment

Preparing the Experiment Venue

In preparing the venue, the researcher tries not to overlook any other intervening factors that might affect the validity of the result of the study. The following will be foreseen intervening factors and how each one will be avoided (Egcas, 2008).

Sitting Arrangement. There will be no pre-determined seat plans imposed. Subjects of the study will be allowed to sit anywhere they wanted so that sitting inconvenience as an intervening factor will be eliminated

Lighting. The experimental venue will be well-lighted during the conduct of experiments. It had four (4) 120 watts fluorescent lamps mounted at the ceiling. These 4 fluorescent lamps will be switched on during the conduct of the study in order to eliminate bad lighting as an intervening factor.

Ventilation. The experimental venue will be equipped with three (3) wall fans. During experiment, this will be turned on so that poor ventilation will be eliminated as intervening factor.

Experimental Procedure

The researcher who handles the English subject is responsible for teaching the subject.

The intervention consists of learning exercises on literacy skills. To protect the study from the Hawthorne Effect- the effect which refers to the tendency of subjects to act differently when they know they will be been studied (Egcas, 2008), the experiments will be made part of the regular classroom meetings for the subject English usually during the 50 minutes of the class period. The research subjects will not be informed that they are the subjects of the study.

Activity Log

The researcher also will utilize activity log to record the activities completed by the research subjects on a daily basis that address their proficiency in completing the competencies required for the subject.

At the end of the two (2) weeks of four periods, the researcher will administer the posttest to the subjects of the study.

Results of the pre and post-tests will be analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Data Analysis

To determine the level of the literacy performance of the learners who will be exposed to the materials to be used during the pretest and posttest, mean will be used. Data will be computed using Window-based SPSS 17.0 version (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) with the help of a qualified statistician.

Results and Discussion

In this section, it can show the presentation, analysis and the interpretation of data.

Demographic Profile of the Grade 1 Learners in terms of Gender.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Grade I learners in terms of Gender*

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	12	52.17
Male	11	47.78
Total	23	100

Table 1 shows that the gender of the respondents. The female was 12 out of 23 learners or 52.17 percent and the male was 11 out of 23 or 47.78 percent.

The Literacy Level of Early Grade learners in Pretest and Posttest

Table 2. *The Literacy Level of Early Grade learners in Pretest and Posttest*

Group	Mean	Std.Deviation	Interpretation
Pretest	14.1304	3.69649	Average
Posttest	24.8261	3.20017	Very High

Scale: ± 1.0 - ± 6.0 , Very Low; ± 7.0 - ± 12.0 , Low; ± 13.0 - ± 18.0 , Average; ± 19.0 - ± 24.0 , High; ± 25.0 - ± 30.0 , Very High.

Reflected in the table are the levels of literacy of the early grades in pretest and posttest. The obtained mean in pretest is 14.1304 while 24.8261 in posttest. The above mean of scores showed that the increase of literacy level is from average to very high. These findings provide evidence on the importance of early intensive evidence-based intervention for reading problems in the primary grades. Further, this finding conforms to the findings of the study on Analysis of Pre Test and Post Test Performance of Students in a Learning Center Model at the Elementary School Level by Schalich (2015), the results indicated that approximately 50% of students who received explicated small group instruction in reading comprehension performed higher on their reading section.

Comparison of the Levels of Literacy in Pretest and Posttest

Another major objective of this study is to determine if there is a significant difference in the literacy level in pretest and post-test. This is presented in table 3.

Table 3. *Comparison of the Levels of Literacy in Pretest and Posttest*

Source of Variation	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	Comp.t	P	Interpretation
Pre-test	14.13	3.6	22	35.918	.000	Highly Significant
Post-tests	24.82	96				

Computed t of 35.918 and its probability value of .000 at .05 level of significance is interpreted that there is a highly significant difference exist between the pre-test and post-test scores of learners. Null hypothesis claiming that there is no significant difference on the literacy levels in pre-test and post-test is therefore rejected. This means that the materials developed for increasing the literacy of early grades learners could significantly increase literacy level, denoting further that the developed materials are effective. This conforms to the study by Denton, et.al. (2014) both intervention groups performed significantly better than control groups on untimed word identification. Significant effects favored over on phonemic decoding and one measure of comprehension.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The female was more frequently than the male.

The above mean of scores showed that the increase of literacy level is from average to very high.

This means that the materials developed for increasing the literacy of early grades learners could significantly increase literacy level, denoting further that the developed materials are effective.

Based on the foregoing conclusion arrived, the researcher recommends the following:

The school should utilize the use of learning module to help develop the literacy level of early grade learners.

Other researches must be conducted considering other variables.

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